

Flexcrash

D1.2 Flexcrash Platform Prototype

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Executive Summary

This document describes the architecture and the design of the Flexcrash platform for organizing user studies to identify relevant mixed traffic scenarios. It also demonstrates the Flexcrash platform's main features: generating and simulating interactive driving scenarios.

Using the Flexcrash platform, regulators, developers, and other interested parties can study the live interaction between human drivers and autonomous vehicles in simulated mixed-traffic scenarios.

The Flexcrash platform implements an online turn-based, multiplayer game that allows remote players, humans and not, to simultaneously participate in driving simulations; thus, it enables live interaction and possibly leads to identifying critical mixed-traffic scenarios. The Flexcrash platform follows established design patterns typical of Web applications to achieve scalability, interoperability, and ease of use.

The Flexcrash platform aims for reusability and generalizability; thus, it relies on open-source frameworks, such as the CommonRoad motion planner benchmarking framework. Consequently, for this demonstration, we use the state-of-the-art, sampling-based motion planner kindly provided by CommonRoad's Principal Investigator, Prof. Matthias Althoff (Technical University of Munich), as reference AV implementation. Other AV implementations can be added to the Flexcrash platform after its release to the public.

Promoting open research and favouring results' replicability are fundamental to Flexcrash; therefore, the Flexcrash platform's code, manuals, and other resources are made publicly available at:

<https://github.com/Flexcrash/web-platform>

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Terminology and Acronyms

<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>AV</i>	<i>Automated Vehicles</i>
<i>REST</i>	<i>Representational State Transfer</i>
<i>HTML</i>	<i>Hypertext Markup Language</i>
<i>JSON</i>	<i>JavaScript Object Notation</i>
<i>API</i>	<i>Application Programming Interface</i>
<i>GUI</i>	<i>Graphical User Interface</i>
<i>CSS</i>	<i>Cascading Style Sheets</i>
<i>URL</i>	<i>Uniform Resource Locator</i>

1. Introduction

Automated vehicles (AVs) aim to drastically improve road safety by eliminating human errors such as traffic rule violations, speeding, and driving under the influence of alcohol or drugs. However, accidents will still occur despite the increasing expected presence of AVs, partly due to the concurrent and mostly conflictual presence of human drivers and automated vehicles on the road, a situation known as *mixed traffic*.

Identifying critical mixed-traffic scenarios, i.e., driving scenarios involving mixed traffic that might lead to crashes or near-crashes, is crucial to supplement existing technical and legal requirements and consumer testing. However, data about critical mixed-traffic scenarios is generally unavailable (Alessio Gambi, 2022).

The Flexcrash platform aims to enable regulators, developers, and other parties to study the *live interactions* between human drivers and AVs in simulated mixed-traffic scenarios. Thus, enabling experimentation of future AVs, the Flexcrash platform can help identify critical mixed-traffic scenarios not yet covered by existing datasets and crash databases.

Studying the live interaction of human drivers and AVs requires a platform that can integrate AVs implemented using different technologies while protecting the intellectual property of their developers, be easy to use by human drivers, and effectively enable humans and automated vehicles to participate in the same simulations. Additionally, such a platform shall scale as many users and AVs are expected to participate in several concurrent simulations.

As planned in Deliverable D5.2. (Interim PUDR, M24), communication and promotion actions will be adopted to increase the visibility of the Flexcrash platform and the number of participants after its public release. Those actions will occur through (i) the project's communication channels (e.g., website, social media, newsletters), (ii) the participation in key national and international conferences, congresses, and fairs, and (iii) the organization of workshops and webinars targeting potential participants.

The Flexcrash platform addresses these main challenges by following the example of scalable Web applications and online multiplayer games that allow many remote players to cooperate and compete. Therefore, to ease the integration of AVs, the Flexcrash platform exposes a set of REST APIs. At the same time, it implements an interactive Graphical User Interface (GUI) to allow human drivers to participate in the simulations.

The Flexcrash project delivers its platform as open-source software to promote further research, platform extensions, and additional contributions from Academia and Industry. The Flexcrash platform uses open-source simulation libraries and state-of-the-art simulation frameworks for the same reasons. The code of the platform, instructions for setup and execution, and additional material (e.g., links to videos demonstrating the Flexcrash platform in action) are available at:

<https://github.com/Flexcrash/web-platform>

1.1 The Flexcrash platform in the context of the Flexcrash project

The Flexcrash project's main goal is to develop a flexible and hybrid manufacturing technology to enhance weight reduction and crash resistance by locally reinforcing the critical areas for a crash event, creating safer and lighter structures than current solutions. In order to validate the proposed solutions, Flexcrash needs data (e.g., impact

angles) about possible crashes involving autonomous vehicles, which in turn requires identifying critical mixed-traffic scenarios.

The Flexcrash platform is a means this project proposes for collecting simulation data about critical driving scenarios involving human drivers and autonomous vehicles. Consequently, the Flexcrash platform develops in the context of WP1, which contributes to describing future relevant crash scenarios and load case requirements (see Deliverable D1.1).

1.2 About this deliverable

Section 2 introduces the main design decisions, software architecture, and details on the technologies and frameworks of the Flexcrash platform. Section 3 illustrates the working of the Flexcrash platform by presenting its main supported Use Cases. Finally, Section 4 reports on ongoing work and lists planned future work.

2. The Flexcrash platform

To validate the effectiveness of safety mechanisms in mixed-traffic scenarios, we need to capture new scenarios, as relying solely on the ones collected in the past might not be representative as those contain barely any data about Avs (State of California, Department of Motor Vehicles, n.d.). The Flexcrash platform aims to fill this gap by observing how human drivers and autonomous vehicles interact while sharing the same (simulated) roads. It does so by implementing a common simulation paradigm suitable for human drivers and AVs, employing remote participation to protect participants' intellectual properties, and building a scalable platform to host many simulations.

2.1 Driving simulations as turn-based strategic games

Human drivers and autonomous vehicles possess diverse reaction times and driving capabilities; hence, defining a common simulation paradigm that allows them to participate effectively in the same driving simulations is challenging.

The solution implemented in the Flexcrash platform is to abstract mixed-traffic driving simulations as turn-based strategy games. In turn-based games, players' interaction is not continuous nor has stringent real-time constraints. On the contrary, the gameplay proceeds stepwise in turns. We argue that such settings ease the remote participation of drivers by masking network delays and reducing the load on human drivers, which are not bound anymore to running driving simulations.

In classic turn-based games, each player performs a move in each turn before leaving the control to the next player. Since this setup does not entirely reflect the truly concurrent nature of driving in traffic, the Flexcrash platform's simulations include elements of the Game theory, effectively making them strategic games. In strategic games, players strive to achieve various --possibly conflicting-- objectives by planning a strategy. In the case of driving simulations, the natural goal is to drive the vehicles safely to a given target location (i.e., goal area) while sharing the road with other traffic participants with the catch that no knowledge about what the other players will do next is available.

The Flexcrash platform creates and maintains scenarios' consistency while the players, i.e., human drivers and autonomous vehicles, play the strategic games by enforcing a well-defined scenario life cycle (more details in Section 3).

2.2 The Flexcrash platform's software architecture

As illustrated by Figure 1, the Flexcrash platform follows the layered architectural style typical of Web applications (Taylor, 2009). According to this architectural style, each layer can only invoke the next lower layer's functions and respond to the next upper layer's requests, i.e., interactions happen only and always between consecutive layers.

Figure 1. Overview of Flexcrash platform's current (left) and target (right) layered architecture.

The Flexcrash platform comprises of four components: Web GUI, Front End, Scenario Management and Execution, and Persistence.

The **Web GUI** interfaces to human drivers and other users, such as scenario owners. This component displays users' controls and captures users' actions, including navigating between the pages, creating new scenarios, visualizing scenarios, and selecting trajectories during the execution of the scenarios. The Web GUI is a client component that runs inside the user devices and interacts with the server-side components by invoking the APIs exposed by the Front End.

The **Front End** receives, validates, and dispatches the requests submitted by the AVs (via the REST APIs) and the users (via the Web GUI) to the underlying layers. Examples of requests processed by this layer include creating new scenarios, joining existing scenarios, and retrieving and rendering scenario states and sampled trajectories.

The **Scenario Management and Execution** layer is the core component of the Flexcrash platform and contains its main business logic, e.g., user authentication and authorization, scenarios life-cycle management, and trajectory sampling and validation.

The **Persistence** interfaces the underlying relational database to store and retrieve data and metadata about users, players, and scenarios.

In the current implementation (Figure 1 – Left), the Flexcrash platform adopts a two-layered architecture (Front End and Scenario Management and Execution belong to the Application Server layer). This architecture is simpler to implement but cannot easily

scale; therefore, for the next release, we plan to adopt the more complex but scalable three-layered architecture reported on the right side of Figure 1.

2.3 Technical specifications

The Flexcrash platform uses several technologies and libraries.

The Web GUI uses the standard technologies of dynamic websites; hence, it includes components written in HTML, CSS, and JavaScript. As libraries, this layer uses jQuery (Open JS Foundation, n.d.), Bootstrap (Bootstrap, n.d.) for styling, and mpld3 (Vanderplas, n.d.) for generating interactive scenarios diagrams.

The other layers of the Flexcrash platform (Front End, Scenario Management and Execution, and Persistence) are implemented using Python. The Front End is built using the Flask framework (Pallets organization, n.d.), the reference framework to develop Web applications in Python, and uses standard libraries to serialize and deserialize Python objects into JSON Strings.

The Scenario Management and Execution uses many packages of the CommonRoad framework (Matthias Althoff, 2017) (i.e., commonroad-io, commonroad-route-planner, commonroad-collision-detector) that implement driving scenarios, road networks, and vehicle trajectories.

The Persistence layer instead uses libraries to access the underlying relational database. In the current implementation, the Flexcrash platform uses MariaDB and SQLite3 (SQLite Consortium, n.d.) as a relational databases for production and development; hence, the Persistence layer requires the sql-alchemy package to interact with it.

Note: the complete list of dependencies and setup instructions are available at <https://github.com/Flexcrash/web-platform/tree/main/documentation>

2.4 Licensing information

The Flexcrash platform adopts a permissive "New BSD License", also called "Modified BSD License," to foster usage and promote research. This license allows almost unlimited freedom with this software. However, it requires including the BSD copyright and license notice in any package using or derived from it. The full text of the license is available at <https://github.com/Flexcrash/web-platform/blob/main/LICENSE>

3. Main Use Cases

The Flexcrash platform implements several Use Cases. The main Use Cases are the creation, joining, execution, and monitoring of mixed-traffic scenarios. The Flexcrash platform also implements additional Use Cases, including user management and authentication, scenarios lookup, and road network template upload. The following sections illustrate how the platform works from the perspective of human drivers, i.e., users that use the Flexcrash platform via the Web GUI. All the reported screenshots come from a running instance of the Flexcrash platform.

3.1 Mixed-traffic scenarios creation

Users can create new mixed-traffic scenarios from the `Create Custom Scenario` page by selecting one of the existing *Road Network Templates* and providing the

necessary details (see Figure 2). A user that creates a scenario becomes that scenario's owner.

Figure 2. The “Create Custom Scenario” page.

The mandatory details for creating mixed-traffic scenarios are the number of human drivers (*Number of Players*) and autonomous vehicles (*Number of AVs*) that will take part in the simulation and the (max) scenario duration (*Duration*). Optionally, scenario owners can pre-select specific human drivers to include automatically in the simulation (*Automatically Registered Users*). Hence, the Flexcrash platform allows users to create *open scenarios* (all registered users can join) and *closed scenarios* (only designated users can join).

Mixed-traffic scenarios that lack players enter a WAITING state (see *Scenario Overview* page in Figure 3) and cannot start until *all* the expected human drivers and AVs have joined it.¹ This constraint helps preventing simulation inconsistencies.

Figure 3. The “Scenario Overview” page. Case: *waiting scenario*.

¹ In the current implementation, autonomous vehicles join the simulations automatically.

Once all the required players join a mixed-traffic scenario, that scenario becomes ACTIVE, and the Scenario Overview page reports a visualization of and links to inspect its states (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Visualization of an active mixed-traffic scenario (for a user driving in that scenario).

3.2 Mixed-traffic scenarios monitoring

As illustrated in Figure 4, users can access information about scenarios on the Scenario Overview page. The Flexcrash platform lets *all users*, not just players and scenario owners, access mixed-traffic scenarios in the spirit of open research. This way, interested parties can access simulation data and run analyses on all the available mixed-traffic scenarios without being bound to participate in any simulation. However, only players and scenario owners can act upon mixed-traffic scenarios, as explained in the next section.

In the top part, the Scenario Overview page reports general metadata about the mixed-traffic scenarios and actions (e.g., “Drive”) available to the users. Scenario metadata include name, max and effective duration, owner username, current status, and username of drivers who have joined.

In the middle part, the Scenario Overview page includes a slider component to visualize the status of the scenario at various simulation steps. This component

visualizes the road network and the vehicles involved in the simulation. Additionally, as Figure 4 illustrates, it highlights the vehicle driven by the current user and its goal area.

Finally, the bottom of the `Scenario Overview` page lists all the scenario states of the simulation. For each state, the page reports whether the state is ACTIVE, DONE, or PENDING. ACTIVE and DONE states are *immutable* as they have already been computed. They represent the current (ACTIVE) and past (DONE) states of the simulation and can be inspected by the users (e.g., by following the provided hyperlinks). PENDING states represent "future" states of the scenario that have yet to be computed; hence, no user can access them, and the `Scenario Overview` page does not provide their hyperlinks. As the simulations progress (see Section 3.3), more states become DONE and ACTIVE; thus, after refreshing the `Scenario Overview` page, users will be able to access the latest states of the scenario.

The state of a scenario at a given simulation step consists of the state of all its participants, i.e., the vehicles, at that simulation step. A vehicle's states include the position, rotation, velocity, acceleration, and status (e.g., ACTIVE, CRASHED, GOAL_REACHED) of that vehicle.

Following the REST paradigm, scenario states are self-standing resources. They are available at specific URLs, e.g., `/state?scenario_id=3×tamp=0`, and own multiple *representations*.² The Flexcrash platform represents scenario states as structured text in JSON format or diagrams. The JSON representation is amenable to automatic processing; thus, it is provided by the REST API to autonomous vehicles. The visual representation, instead, is more suited for human drivers; hence, it is accessible using the Web GUI (see `Scenario State` page in Figure 5).

Figure 5. Visualization of a scenario state (for a user driving in that scenario).

The `Scenario State` page shows a simplified view of scenario states that consists of the visualization of the scenario state (as in the `Scenario Overview` page) and details about the vehicles in the scenarios. These details include the username of their drivers, the current speed of the vehicles, and whether the vehicles are accelerating or braking.

² The URLs of the scenario states are those reported in the `Scenario Overview` page for ACTIVE and DONE states.

The `Scenario State` page also includes a set of buttons to navigate among the various scenario states (i.e., *Show Previous State* and *Show Next State*) or going back to the `Scenario Overview` page (*Back to Scenario Overview*).

3.3 Mixed-traffic scenarios evolution

Using information about a scenario's current and past states, drivers plan a sequence of "future" vehicle states to drive their vehicles toward the assigned goal areas, i.e., they plan a *driving trajectory*. Next, players submit the driving trajectories to the Flexcrash platform that collects and validates them (e.g., they must contain at least one "future" vehicle state). Only after all the players have submitted valid driving trajectories can the Flexcrash platform evolve the scenario.

Scenario evolution consists in (I) applying the planned states scheduled at each simulation step to the vehicles to update their physical state (i.e., position, rotation, velocity, and acceleration) and (II) checking whether vehicles reached the goal area or collided.

Vehicles that reach their designated goal areas "disappear" from the simulation as they have completed their driving task. In contrast, vehicles involved in collisions are *disabled*, i.e., they cannot move anymore, but remain in the scenario until the scenario is over. In other words, crashed vehicles become *static obstacles*. Figure 6 illustrates how the Flexcrash platform visualizes collided vehicles using a thick red border (Figure 6-A) and vehicles that reached their goal area using a thick black border and making them transparent (Figure 6-B).

Figure 6. Visualization of collided vehicles (A) and vehicles that reached their goal area (B).

Every time the Flexcrash platform computes a new scenario state, that state becomes `ACTIVE`. Active states are *immutable* and stored into the relational database.

The submitted driving trajectories must include at least one state to make scenarios evolve. However, their *size*, i.e., the number of "future" states they include, is not predefined or fixed for players. Hence, different players can submit trajectories of different sizes, thus mimicking short- and long-term planning, and the same player can submit trajectories of different sizes at any time. Nevertheless, the Flexcrash platform truncates trajectories exceeding the scenarios' maximum duration.

Players can (partially) update the submitted trajectories if their updates only modify "future" vehicle states, i.e., `PENDING` states. Notably, replanting a previously computed

trajectory is fundamental to allowing drivers to adjust their strategies, for instance, when fresh data about the other vehicles becomes available.

3.4 Ending mixed-traffic scenarios

The Flexcrash platform monitors the execution of scenarios and ensures that their simulation ends as soon as any of the following properties hold:

- A. The simulation reaches its max duration.
- B. All the vehicles have either reached their goal area or crashed.

Once scenarios stop, they become *immutable*. Consequently, users can visualize them (see Figure 7) and inspect their states; however, users cannot change them.

Figure 7. The “Scenario Overview” page (Case: ended scenario)

The only exception is scenario owners that can always delete their scenarios from the Home page (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. The “Home” page.

3.5 Trajectories sampling

Taking active part into a mixed-traffic scenario simulation requires to plan driving trajectories. Autonomous vehicles compute the driving trajectories *locally* and submit them to the Flexcrash platform via the appropriate REST API calls (e.g., a POST request to `/scenarios/1/drivers/1/states/`). This way, the Flexcrash platform remains agnostic of AV implementations. Moreover, it protects AV developers' intellectual properties since they do not have to share their code with the platform.

Computing valid driving trajectories is not trivial and requires fiddling with complex kinematics computations that not all human drivers might master. Consequently, requiring users to compute and input trajectories *manually* would strongly limit the number of human drivers that could participate in the simulations, effectively defeating the purpose of the Flexcrash platform. Hence, to avoid this situation, the Flexcrash platform adopts a simplified approach for letting human drivers planning driving trajectories: *trajectory sampling*. Nevertheless, in the current version, expert human drivers can still submit “manually computed” trajectories using the REST APIs. Extending the Web GUI to allow submitting user-defined trajectories is planned for the next release of the Flexcrash platform.

Given the current state of a scenario and knowing which goal area a vehicle driven by a human should reach, the Flexcrash platform samples valid driving trajectories and proposes them to the human drivers via the Web GUI (see Figure 9). Thanks to an interactive component of the Web GUI, human drivers can navigate among the sampled trajectories by changing few parameters, select the most suitable one, and visualize the available (dashed blue) and selected (solid black) trajectories.

Figure 9. Interactive visualization of a scenario state (for a user driving in that scenario) with trajectory sampling.

As illustrated in Figure 9, human drivers can navigate among the various trajectories by using the Previous Trajectory and Next Trajectory buttons, or by selecting the sampling parameters using the sliders. The available sampling parameters include setting the target speed (Velocity) and lateral displacement (Move Displacement) to reach in future states, and the time to reach them (which controls for instance the sharpness of lateral movements). The last parameter, Planning Horizon, decides how many “future” states of the selected trajectory to submit to the Flexcrash platform and is visualized as a thick solid line (see Figure 10). Note that the interactive component allows the users to zoom in and out of the diagram; hence, they can more easily distinguish the trajectories and select the preferred one among the many sampled trajectories.

Figure 10. Trajectory sampling detailed view.

The dashed-blue lines represent the sampled trajectories, the solid thin line represents the currently selected trajectory, and the thick border represents the planning horizon. Planning (A) contains fewer states than planning (B); hence, the thick black line is shorter.

We argue that visualizing and selecting trajectories is a more intuitive, albeit less flexible, approach to letting human drivers drive simulated vehicles.

3.6 Other Use Cases

The Flexcrash platform supports additional (supporting) use cases. However, for the sake of brevity, this deliverable does not extensively describe them. Videos demonstrating them are available at:

<https://github.com/Flexcrash/web-platform/tree/main/videos>

Use Case: Sign up. New users can register to the platform using the REST API. Once registered, the users can create, visualize and join scenarios. User can register using the `Sign Up` page or the REST API.

Use Case: User Authentication. Registered users must log in the Flexcrash platform using the `Log In` page or authenticate themselves using the REST API before creating, joining, and observing scenarios. Notably, all the users must accept that the data collected by the Flexcrash platform will be used for research purposes.

Use Case: Scenario Lookup. The Flexcrash platform allows registered users to lookup scenarios in different ways. For instance, users can lookup scenarios that they own (`Scenarios Created by You` page), scenarios in which they are driving (`Scenarios You Are In` page), and scenarios that they can join (`Join Waiting Scenarios` page).

Use Case: Delete Scenario. Scenario owners can delete their scenarios. In this case, the Flexcrash platform removes all the data about the deleted scenarios, including entries in the relational database and scenario visualizations.

Use Case: Upload of road network templates. Road network templates can be uploaded to the Flexcrash platform (currently, only via the REST APIs). Once uploaded, the templates are visible on the `Create Custom Scenario` page.

4. Summary and Future Work

In the current first version, the Flexcrash platform implements the main functionalities to study live interactions of human drivers and autonomous vehicles in a prototypical way. Therefore, it is suitable for running small pilots and controller studies. Improving the robustness and scalability of the platform to conduct larger studies is part of future work. Additionally, installing and setting up the Flexcrash platform's requirements (e.g., SQLite3, CommonRoad) and the TUM's code (not yet openly available) requires manual effort.

Besides continuously improving the Flexcrash platform's code quality by identifying and fixing bugs, *ongoing work* aims to improve the platform's deployability, availability, and usability. Regarding *deployability*, we plan to package the platform and all its dependencies in (Docker) containers so interested parties can run the platform with a simple command. Regarding *availability*, we plan to deploy an instance of the Flexcrash platform on a publicly reachable server to allow open studies. Regarding *usability*, we plan to conduct user studies, improve the Web GUI, and develop a basic REST API client to help AV developers bootstrap the integration of their driving agents with the platform. Particularly relevant updates include implementing an interactive scenario generation plugin, an improved trajectory sampling and visualization logic, and a component to upload road network templates.

Longer-term plans, instead, include the integration of the Flexcrash platform with full-fledged driving simulators like BeamNG.tech (BeamNG GmbH, n.d.) to improve the driving simulations' accuracy and enable the use of Deep Learning-based driving agents.

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